

Ichthyop practical session

Christophe Lett

Marco Andrello

Nicolas Barrier

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1 Getting started

1.1 Install Java

Ichthyop is a Java program. Therefore, Java is required.

- Download the most recent version of Java here: <https://www.oracle.com/java/technologies/downloads/>
- Install Java
- Open a Terminal or a Cmd prompt and type:

```
java -version
```

 Warning

Java > 11 is required!

1.2 Install NetCDF

Ichthyop also need the NetCDF-C library to run.

Linux

Open a Terminal and type:

```
sudo apt install netcdf4
```

Mac Os X

Open a Terminal and type:

```
sudo port install netcdf4
```

Windows

Download the pre-built libraries in [Unidata website](#)

 Warning

During the install process, make sure that the location of the library is added to the PATH

1.3 Download Ichthyop

- Create a `ichthyop` folder
- Go to <https://github.com/ichthyop/ichthyop/releases/latest>
- Download the `ichthyop-X.Y.Z-jar-with-dependencies.jar` binary file.

1.4 Download hydrographic files

- Download the hydrographic on the Ichthyop Zenodo Community: <https://zenodo.org/records/10890690>
- Unzip the archive file

1.5 Running Ichthyop

Windows

- Double-click on the `ichthyop-X.Y.Z-jar-with-dependencies.jar` file.

Linux/Mac Os X

- On the Terminal, navigate to the location of the `ichthyop-X.Y.Z-jar-with-dependencies.jar` file using `cd`
- Type `java -jar ichthyop-X.Y.Z-jar-with-dependencies.jar &`

2 First simulation

2.1 Creation new configuration

- Create a new configuration file by clicking on the `New` button (Figure 1)

2.2 Choosing template

- Select the `ROMS 3D` template and click on `Create` (Figure 2)

2.3 Running the simulation

- Run the simulation by clicking on the `Run simulation` button (Figure 3)

Figure 1: New configuration

Figure 2: Choosing template

Figure 3: Running simulation

2.4 Visualization

- Visualise the results by clicking on the **Make maps** button (Figure 4)

2.5 Expected results

You should see larval dispersal off Cape Town in South Africa (Figure 5).

3 New simulations

3.1 Exploring configuration file

- Explore the different processes and parameters contained in the configuration file and their default values (Figure 6)

3.2 Deactivating advection

- In the configuration file, go to:

- Disable advection by clicking on the **Enabled** tick box
- Save the configuration file by clicking the **Save** button.

Figure 4: Mapping outputs

Figure 5: Outputs of the first simulation (advection)

Figure 6: Exploring configuration file

Warning

Remember to save it after every change

- Run the simulation
- Draw map
- **What happens?**

3.3 Playing with advection/diffusion

- Repeat the operations above by activating only diffusion
- Repeat the operations above by activating both advection/diffusion

(a) No advection/No diffusion

(b) No advection/Diffusion

(c) Advection/Diffusion

Figure 7: Results of the different Ichthyop configurations

3.4 Vertical migration

- In the Mapping section, choose to represent the `depth` variable, with values -50, -30 and -10 m for min., med. and max., respectively.
- Click on `Make maps`
- In the configuration file, go to:

- Read the explanations at the top of the block. Click on `Enabled` and look at the default values of the parameters.

3.5 Vertical migration

- Run the simulation with larval vertical migration. Note that the depth of larvae is now changing according to the vertical scheme specified, but that this movement has almost no effect on the overall larval distribution (Figure 8b).
- Change the vertical migration scheme such that larvae stay at -50 m depth day and night. Note that there is now a (small) effect (Figure 8c)
- Go back to the initial situation by unselecting vertical migration

Figure 8: Different migration configurations. (a) No migration (b) Migration between -10 and -30 m (c) Constant depth (-50 m)

3.6 Growth

- Go to:

- Read the explanations at the top of the block and activate growth
- Run the simulation and visualise the `length` variable using `Auto range` for the values and colours
- Go to:

- Read the explanations at the top of the block.
- Visualise the `stage` variable using `Auto range` for the values and colours.

3.7 Initial positions in a text file

Unselect vertical migration and growth. Go to

Select, click on the **Edit** button inside the **Value** field and create the file proposed by default (`benguela_drifters.txt`); it contains the initial positions of all individuals. Run the simulation and observe the individuals locations.

Open the `plot_traj_Ichthyop_v3_TP` function in the R software. Try to understand the code.

Go to:

in Ichthyop to understand why the value of `lasttime` is 61 in the R function. Adjust the path to the last file (ncdf format, `.nc`) created by Ichthyop in the `ichthyop-3.2b\output` directory of your computer. Install the R packages `ncdf` and `maps` if necessary, then execute the function (Figure 9). Make the necessary changes in the R function to plot only the last positions of individuals and check that they are the same as those plotted in the graphic interface of Ichthyop.

Figure 9: Trajectories simulated in Ichthyop and plotted in R

3.8 Release zones

In Ichthyop, unselect

and select:

Edit the default file (`benguela_zones.xml`); it contains the release zones (**Release**) and the destination zones (**Recruitment**). These zones are defined by the geographic coordinates of a polygon, two isobaths (**Bathymetric mask**) and upper and lower depth (**Thickness**). Run the simulation (check with **Preview** that the release zone appears) and visualise larval depth. Do it again after changing the values of isobaths first to 500 and 1000 m instead of 200 and 500 m, then with 1000 and 2000 m (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Final distribution of larvae and their depth (from red -15 m to white -7.5 m to green 0 m) for a release zone (purple polygon) located between the isobaths (a) 200–500 m (b) 500–1000 m (c) 1000–2000 m.

3.9 Destination zones

Define now 3 different release zones, each corresponding to one of the 3 seen before (click on to add a new zone). Select **Advanced - Biology - Recruitment - In zones**. Edit the zone file and look at the parameters defining recruitment and at the recruitment zone. What is the distinction between a release zone and a recruitment zone? Check with **Preview** that the 3 release zones and the destination zone appear.

In **Main - Time**, add two new release dates for days 8 and 13 (same year, month and hour) by clicking on **Add value**. In **Main - Output**, change the directory in which the simulation results are stored to `output\TP1`. Save, run the simulation, this time there are 3 simulations, one for each release date.

Open the `compute_recruitment_Ichthyop_v3_TP` function in the R software. Adjust the path to the TP1 directory, install the XML package if necessary, then execute the function (Figure 11a).

Go back to Ichthyop and visualise the trajectories of individuals for the first release date (Figure 11b). Note that in the end there is no individual inside the destination area! Look again at the parameters used for recruitment to understand why the percentage of individuals transported from the release zones to the destination zone, as computed with the R function, is not zero.

Figure 11: Mean (and standard error of the mean) transport success from 3 release zones to a destination zone, for 3 release dates. The zones are shown in (b) with the final distribution of individuals for the first release date.

Add now 2 new destination zones defined by isobaths 200–300 m and 300–500 m respectively. To avoid that individuals recruit in several zones, change `Stop moving when recruited` to `True`. In Main - Output, change the directory in which the simulation results are stored to `output\TP2`. Save, run the simulation.

Open the `compute_connectivity_Ichthyop_v3_TP` function in the R software. Adjust the path to the TP2 directory, install the fields and spam packages if necessary, then execute the function (Figure 12a). Go back to Ichthyop and visualise the trajectories of individuals for the first release date (Figure 12b). Note that the final positions of individuals in the north are very different in Figure 11b and (Figure 12b). Why?

3.10 Dispersal distances

In TP2, delete the folder containing the simulation maps of the previous simulation, leaving only the 3 .nc files (that correspond to the 3 release dates). In the R software, open the `compute_distances_Ichthyop_v3_TP` function and adjust the path to the TP2 directory. Install the sp package if necessary and then execute the function (Figure 13). Do the same for TP1 (change the values of `xlim` and `ylim` in the `hist` function of R if necessary).

Figure 12: Mean transport success (a) from 3 release zones to 3 destination zones, for 3 release dates. The zones are shown in (b) with the final distribution of individuals for the first release date.

Figure 13: Histograms of dispersal distances for the 3 files (corresponding here to 3 release dates).

3.11 Backtracking

From the final positions of the simulated drifters trajectories (`Initial positions in a text file` section above), we're going to backtrack (i.e., track backwards in time) each drifter to its initial location.

In Main - Advanced - Release, choose the `restart mode`. Read the explanation of the block and choose the NetCDF file that corresponds to the output of the drifters simulation performed before. If you forgot which file it is, or deleted it, then do it again!

In Main - Time, click on `Show hidden parameters` and for `Direction of the simulation` select `backward` instead of `forward`. Now we need to adjust the time for `Beginning of the simulation` to make it correspond to the end of the simulation performed forward in time, i.e. year 01 month 05 day 18.

Save, run the simulation and then plot the trajectories using the same script as before. Note that the trajectories are perfectly back-simulated (compare Figure 14 with Figure 9) except for a few of them which are missing (because the individuals were `dead` at the end of the simulation forward in time, for reaching the border of the domain).

Figure 14: Trajectories backtracked in Ichthyop and plotted in R